

SHOULD TAXES BE VISIBLE OR HIDDEN? AN ECONOMIC AND ETHICAL LOOK AT A PUBLIC FINANCE ISSUE

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Abstract

This paper examines the question of whether taxes should be visible or hidden from various ethical perspectives. The author concludes that hiding taxes from taxpayers is always unethical.

Introduction

A tax can be either visible or hidden. The two possibilities seem to be diametrically opposed to each other. Which possibility is better? That depends on the goals of the individual making the determination. If the goal is to raise as much revenue as possible with a minimum of protest, then a hidden tax is to be preferred to a visible tax. If the goal is to restrain the amount of tax the government takes, or to let taxpayers know exactly what they have to pay for government services, then a visible tax is more likely to help achieve that goal. The real question is whether hiding taxes from those who pay them is ethical.

An Ethical Approach to the Question

¹ Seton Hall University. The author would like to thank the two anonymous referees for their comments and suggestions. Some of the ideas expressed in this article were also expressed in Robert W. McGee, *Some Tax Advice for Latvia and Other Similarly Situated Emerging Democracies*, 13 INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER 223-308 (1996). The author can be reached at bob@dumontinst.com.

There are basically just two ethical approaches to this question. One can take either a utilitarian approach or a rights approach.

There are several variations of utilitarianism, the philosophy that nearly all economists espouse. But basically, utilitarianism holds that an act is ethical if the result is the greatest good for the greatest number. Acts that do not result in the greatest good for the greatest number are unethical.

Bentham, one of the founders of utilitarianism, stated that "...it is the greatest happiness of the greatest number that is the measure of right and wrong."² Sidgwick, a later utilitarian, said that "...an action is right if and only if it brings about at least as much net happiness as any other action the agent could have performed; otherwise it is wrong."³ According to this view, if an act results in increasing happiness by 10 percent, the act is unethical if another act could have increased happiness by more than 10 percent.⁴

Another variant of utilitarianism, one that economists generally espouse, is that an action is moral if it is efficient. Efficiency and morality are not inconsistent.⁵ The problem with this view is that it totally ignores rights. An action can increase

² Jeremy Bentham, *A fragment on government*, in THE WORKS OF JEREMY BENTHAM, VOL. 1, 227 (J. BOWRING, ED. 1962), as cited in WILLIAM H. SHAW, CONTEMPORARY ETHICS: TAKING ACCOUNT OF UTILITARIANISM 8 (1999).

³ Quoted in SHAW, *supra*, at 10.

⁴ One problem with any utilitarian approach is that it is impossible to measure increases in happiness. It is also not possible to measure interpersonal utility. Measurement problems also result if a few individuals stand to gain a lot from an act while many people stand to lose just a little. Such is the case with tariffs, quotas and other trade restraints.

⁵ RICHARD A. POSNER, ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW 284-285 (5TH ED., 1998). A variation on the utilitarian theme is the wealth maximization view, which holds that "...the criterion for judging whether acts and institutions are just or good is whether they maximize the wealth of society." RICHARD A. POSNER, THE ECONOMICS OF JUSTICE 115 (1983).

efficiency and still be unethical if it violates rights but utilitarianism ignores this possibility.⁶

Ignoring the flaws of the utilitarian approach, let's apply utilitarian theory to the question of whether taxes should be visible or hidden. Hidden taxes reduce administration costs. It costs more to administer a tax if taxpayers know about it. Hiding taxes increases efficiency in tax collection because taxpayers do not protest what they do not know exists. Thus, it would appear that hidden taxes are ethical, since the result is increased efficiency.

However, that is not the end of the analysis. If more taxes are collected, which is likely if the tax is hidden from taxpayers, less money remains in the private sector. Since money is always spent more efficiently in the private sector than by government, one may logically conclude that a transfer of money from the private sector to the government reduces efficiency. Resources are transferred from more highly valued uses to less highly valued uses. Thus, one may conclude that hiding taxes from taxpayers is unethical on utilitarian grounds because it reduces efficiency.

From a rights perspective, a visible tax is to be preferred to a hidden tax. That is because taxpayers have a right to know what they are paying for. Disclosure should be as full and complete as possible. Disclosure is required on corporate financial statements so investors will know something about the stock they are buying. Product labeling laws force manufacturers to disclose the contents of the package.⁷ Bankers are required by law to reveal the full

⁶ That is the fatal flaw in the utilitarian philosophy. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law and Economics*, COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS 209-223 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, 14 NORTHWESTERN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW & BUSINESS 549-565 (1994).

⁷ I am not advocating that there should be labeling laws, but am merely using labeling laws as an example. Free speech advocates would be quick to point out that forcing companies to disclose the contents or ingredients of their products violates their right to free speech, or the right to refrain from speech. In cases where pharmaceutical companies must reveal the contents of their drug, there is

interest charges on the loans they make. And people should know the full cost of what they have to pay for government. If they don't, they will not be able to make intelligent decisions at election time, when they are called upon to decide who their political leaders will be.

Some Examples

An example of a hidden tax would be the value-added tax.⁸ The value-added tax is hidden because the people who ultimately pay it -- consumers -- do not know what portion of their purchase is for the product and what portion is for the tax. As a result, they may tend to blame the company that makes or sells the product for the high price, when in fact a significant portion of the price represents a tax.

Excise taxes on alcohol, tobacco and gasoline could be used for examples of hidden taxes. Although the tax may be stated on the package or gas pump, consumers seldom read these things. The tax they pay is part of the stated price.

An example of a visible tax would be a user fee. If people have to pay \$4 to enter a national park, they are made aware immediately of the cost of that particular government service. It is not hidden. But if admission is free, the real cost is hidden. Someone has to pay to maintain the park, to pay the salaries of the employees who work there, and so forth. If the cost of maintaining the park is funded through general tax revenues, those who use the park for free are being subsidized at the expense of everyone else. The result is overuse of the park. If individuals had to pay the full cost of using the facility, fewer of them would use it, which would have beneficial effects on the environment, which is being harmed by overuse of government-owned recreational facilities.

also a possibility that their property rights are being violated, since they have a property right -- a patent -- for the products they produce.

⁸ For more on the value added tax, see ADRIAN OGLEY, *PRINCIPLES OF VALUE ADDED TAX: A EUROPEAN PERSPECTIVE* (1998); ALAN A. TAIT, *VALUE ADDED TAX: INTERNATIONAL PRACTICE AND PROBLEMS* (1988).

Some taxes are partly visible and partly hidden. For example, the personal income tax in the USA is collected by having the employer take the tax directly from employee paychecks before they even receive their pay. The amount of the tax taken is disclosed on their pay stub, but they do not feel the full "bite" of the tax because they never actually saw the money. The tax would be more visible if the employer did not take it out of their checks, since they would then have to write out a check to the government for the amount they owe. Such a requirement would place more pressure on politicians to keep taxes low, since taxpayers would have a better feel for what they are actually paying for government services. But it would also increase collection problems, since not everyone would pay the tax when it is supposed to be paid.

But where there is a tradeoff between disclosure and efficiency, the only ethical choice would be disclosure. If the government is the servant of the people, then the people should know exactly how much their servant costs. The full cost should not be hidden, even if the tax collection process would run more smoothly without disclosure. In the long-run, a full disclosure system would probably result in lower taxes, since taxpayers who are aware of the full cost of government will have a tendency to put pressure on their representatives to keep taxes low.

Concluding Comments

The question of whether a hidden tax is ethical can be viewed from the perspectives of utilitarianism or rights theory. Utilitarianism yields mixed results because, on the one hand, hidden taxes are more efficient to collect than visible taxes because they entail fewer administrative problems and cause the tax collection process to be more efficient. But on the other hand, hiding taxes makes it easier to collect more taxes, which reduces happiness, since all taxes are forced takings, which require taxpayers to forcibly part with a portion of their property.

Applying rights theory to the question produces more clear-cut results. Hiding taxes from those who must pay them is

unethical because taxpayers have a right to know what they pay for the cost of government. Thus, hiding taxes from taxpayers is always unethical, even if hiding them makes tax collection more efficient.